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Correlation of population dynamics of fruit fly *Bactrocera correcta* (Bezzi) on Guava (*Psidium guajava* L.)

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Abstract :

Guava (Psidium guajava L.) originated in tropical America. In India guava is well adapted in almost all the states. Cultivation suited tropical and sub-tropical climatic conditions in various types of soil. In India, the total cultivation area of guava is about 2.66 lakhs hectare with annual production of crop is 4.07 million tons. The productivity of guava crop decline due to various insect pest infestation. Bactrocera spp. is marked as most fruit crop damaging fly. This experiment was conducted to explore the seasonal fluctuation of fruit in the guava crop. The observation made throughout experimental period to reveal the correlation of population of guava fruit fly Bactrocera correcta (Bezzi) with five varieties of guava fruit crop with temperature and relative humidity. It was only Maximum Temperature which showed positive but non-significant correlation, multiple correlation coefficient was found ($R=0.618$) positive and significant at least 5 per cent level of significance in Allahabad Safeda variety. The multiple correlation coefficient was found ($R=0.596$) in Lucknow-49, respectively.

Keywords : Guava, Fruit fly, Weather factors, population dynamics.

Introduction :

Guava (*Psidium guajava* L.) thoroughly naturalized throughout the world in the tropics and sub-tropics. It is popularly known as “poor man’s apple” or “Apple of tropics”. It can be grown successfully in a variety of soil and climatic conditions (Jayanthi and Verghese, 2011). It is one of the important and popular fruit crop belongs to the family Myrtaceae. Guava is a native crop of Central America and introduced to India of Portuguese during the 17th century. It is believed to have originated in Central America (Hayes 1953) and introduced to India. In India, guava is the fourth largest commercially cultivated fruit crop and contributes about 4.0 per cent of total food production (Singh, 1970 and Kapoor, 2005). Low guava productivity is due to several insect pest problems (Jalaluddin et al; 2001). Guava is attacked by about 80 species of insect pest and mites. The most common regular insect pests which attacks guava crop are fruit flies of *Bactrocera correcta* (Bezzi) and it can destroy 80% crop of guava (Mani and Krishnamoorthy, 2000). Insect-pest causes huge damage to the guava fruits (Jalaluddin et al; 2004). The seasonal variation such as temperature, relative humidity and rainfall, etc. plays an important role in the population dynamics (Kaul and Kesar, 2003). Guava fruit fly not only decline the productivity but it destroy other fruit crops also (Kapoor, V.C. 1993) such as mango, peaches, etc.

Material and Methods :

The experiment based on the various species of fruit crop varieties, population dynamics with weather parameters in the orchards of guava. The experiment was conducted about variety Allahabad Safeda, Lucknow-49, Apple colour, Red Flesh and Local seedling. Experiment carried out at the river bed area of Ganga, Bithoor, Kanpur.

Experimental Findings :

The data of the correlation of population dynamics of fruit fly *Bactrocera correcta* were calculated by multiple regression analyses have been analysed and presented in the Table 1 to 4.

Variety Allahabad Safeda :

Data of the Table-1 shows that Maximum Temperature (-0.207), Minimum Temperature (-0.448) and Relative Humidity (-0.458) showed negative correlation. Partial regression coefficient also revealed negative correlation with Minimum temperature (-0.450) and Relative Humidity (-0.105). It was only Maximum Temperature which showed positive but non-significant correlation, multiple correlation coefficient was found ($R=0.618$) positive and significant at least 5 per cent level of significance. This indicates that the dependent variable of average incidence was jointly correlated with Maximum Temperature, Minimum Temperature and Relative Humidity.

Variety Lucknow-49 :

Data of the Table-2 revealed that Maximum Temperature (-0.274), Minimum Temperature (-0.456) and Relative Humidity (-0.427) had negative correlation. Minimum Temperature and Relative Humidity was found significant at 5 per cent level of significance. In the partial regression coefficient Maximum Temperature (-0.275), Minimum Temperature (-0.072) and Relative Humidity (-0.336) showed negative value. It was found non-significant at 5 per cent level of significance. The multiple correlation coefficient was found $R=0.596$. It was significant at 5 per cent level of significance. Dependent variables average incidence was jointly correlated with Maximum Temperature, Minimum Temperature and Relative Humidity, variable was found about 35 per cent.

Variety Apple Colour :

Data of the Table-3 shows that Apple colour variety of guava infected with *Bactrocera correcta*, population was correlated with Maximum Temperature, Minimum Temperature and Relative Humidity. It was found that all the variables revealed negative and non-significant correlation, partial regression coefficient was found negative and non-significant at 5 per cent level of significance with Maximum Temperature (-0.69) and Minimum Temperature (-0.227). Relative Humidity was also found non-significant (0.002). Multiple correlation coefficient was found $R=0.408$. It was also non-significant which indicated that Maximum Temperature, Minimum Temperature and Relative Humidity were not jointly correlated with each other.

Variety Red Flesh :

Table-4 exhibited the results of multiple regression analysis of the data relating to population of *Bactrocera correcta*. It is observed that Maximum Temperature (0.075) showed positive correlation, It was found non-significant. Minimum Temperature (-0.102) and Relative Humidity (-0.367) revealed negative and non-significant. Partial regression coefficient was found non-significant. Multiple correlation coefficient ($R = 0.385$) showed non-significant results.

Variety Local Seedling :

Data of Table-5 the correlation of population dynamics of *Bactrocera correcta* observed that Maximum Temperature (0.267) and Minimum Temperature (0.210) revealed positive correlation. However, Relative Humidity showed negative correlation (-0.034). Partial regression coefficient showed positive correlation with Maximum Temperature (0.732) and relative Humidity (0.194). Minimum Temperature showed negative correlation. Maximum Temperature showed significant results at 5 per cent level of significance. The multiple correlation coefficient ($R=0.324$) was found non-significant at 5 per cent level of significance. This indicated that the dependent variables, average population was not correlated with Maximum Temperature, Minimum Temperature and Relative Humidity.

Results and Discussion :

Population of *Bactrocera correcta* was observed and correlated with Temperature and Relative Humidity with Multiple Regression Analysis methods. It was found that in Allahabad Safeda variety, Maximum Temperature, Minimum Temperature and Relative Humidity exhibited negative correlation in partial regression coefficient. In the Lucknow-49, variety, multiple correlation was also found positive. In the Apple colour variety, population was negatively correlated with Temperature and Relative Humidity. Similarly Red Flesh variety multiple correlation coefficient was found non-significant ($R=0.385$). In the local seedling guava, maximum temperature (0.267) and minimum temperature (0.210) showed positive correlation. However Relative Humidity revealed negative correlation (-0.034).

Table 1 : Correlation of Population of Guava fruit fly (*Bactrocera correcta* Bezzi) with temperature and relative humidity.

1. Dependent Variables - Variety Allahabad Safeda
2. Independent Variables -

Independent Variables	Correlation Coef. with Y	Partial Regression Coef. byx	S.E. of byx	t Value
Max. Temp. X_1	-0.207	0.339	0.443	0.766
Min. Temp. X_2	-0.448	-0.450	0.332	-1.354
RH X_3	-0.458	-0.105	0.161	0.650
	DF = 27			DF = 24

$R = 0.618^*$, $R^2 = 0.381924$ or 38.19%, $F(3, 24) = 4.938$

Multiple regression equation-

$Y = 27.175 + 0.339X_1 - 0.450X_2 - 0.105$

Table 2 : Correlation of Population of Guava fruit fly (*Bactrocera correcta* Bezzi) with temperature and relative humidity.

1. Dependent Variables - Variety Lucknow -49
2. Independent Variables -

Independent Variables	Correlation Coef. with Y	Partial Regression Coef. byx	S.E. of byx	t Value
Max. Temp. X_1	-0.274	-0.275	0.586	-0.469
Min. Temp. X_2	-0.456*	-0.072	0.439	-0.164
RH X_3	-0.427*	-0.336	0.213	-1.579
	DF = 27			DF = 24

$R = 0.596^*$, $R^2 = 0.355216$ or 35.52%, $F(3, 24) = 4.398$

Multiple regression equation-

$Y = 56.176 - 0.275X_1 - 0.072X_2 - 0.336$

Table 3 : Correlation of Population of Guava fruit fly (*Bactrocera correcta* Bezzi) with temperature and relative humidity.

1. Dependent Variables - Variety Apple Colour
2. Independent Variables -

Independent Variables	Correlation Coef. with Y	Partial Regression Coef. byx	S.E. of byx	t Value
Max. Temp. X_1	-0.378	-0.069	0.681	-0.101
Min. Temp. X_2	-0.406	-0.227	0.510	-0.445
RH X_3	-0.015	0.002	0.247	0.007
	DF = 27			DF = 24

$R = 0.408, R^2 = 0.166464$ or 16.64%, $F(3, 24) = 1.600$

Multiple regression equation-

$Y = 24.603 - 0.069X_1 - 0.227X_2 + 0.002$

Table 4 : Correlation of Population of Guava fruit fly (*Bactrocera correcta* Bezzi) with temperature and relative humidity.

1. Dependent Variables - Variety Red Flesh
2. Independent Variables -

Independent Variables	Correlation Coef. with Y	Partial Regression Coef. byx	S.E. of byx	t Value
Max. Temp. X_1	0.075	0.185	0.352	0.525
Min. Temp. X_2	-0.102	-0.155	0.264	-0.586
RH X_3	-0.367	-0.067	0.128	-0.526
	DF = 27			DF = 24

$R = 0.385^*, R^2 = 0.148225$ or 14.82%, $F(3, 24) = 1.389$

Multiple regression equation-

$Y = 19.206 + 0.185X_1 - 0.155X_2 - 0.067$

Table 5 : Correlation of Population of Guava fruit fly (*Bactrocera correcta* Bezzi) with temperature and relative humidity.

1. Dependent Variables - Variety Local Seedling
2. Independent Variables -

Independent Variables	Correlation Coef. with Y	Partial Regression Coef. byx	S.E. of byx	t Value
Max. Temp. X_1	0.267	0.732	0.589	10.243
Min. Temp. X_2	0.210	-0.409	0.441	-0.927
RH X_3	-0.034	0.194	0.214	0.907
	DF = 27			DF = 24

$R = 0.324, R^2 = 0.104976$ or 10.49%, $F(3, 24) = 0.940$

Multiple regression equation-

$Y = 12.180 + 0.732X_1 - 0.409X_2 + 0.194$

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